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REPOSITIONING USERS WITH SMART ARTIFACTS AS PARTICIPANTS IN COLLECTIVE ACTION

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ABSTRACT

To cope effectively with everyday situations it is necessary to understand what the world affords to us. But, it is also fundamental to understand the meaning of one's action in the ecology of actions performed by human and nonhuman participants. We propose to dislocate the user's central position in a system and distribute his or her hegemony in a network of human and nonhuman participants. From this perspective, we offer a triadic structure of social relationships of human-artifact collectives as the minimal unit of analysis from which sociality, social action, and interactive complexity are enacted. We conclude by defining a theoretical-conceptual framework for the design of smart artifacts that can enable social interaction.

Keywords: interaction design, distributed interaction, smart artifacts, social interaction, Actor-Network Theory.

INTRODUCTION

Post-humanist thinkers such as Callon, Law (see, e.g., Callon & Law, 1995), Latour (see, e.g., Latour, 2005) and Knorr-Cetina (Schatzki, Knorr-Cetina & Savigny, 2001) contend that we are increasingly living in an object-centered society where the roles of objects are not only defined as commodities or equipment but also acting as mediators, elements of cohesion, and common places of characterization of one's self. Following this strand of thought, artifacts are not merely tools but activity partakers in human-object collectives. Whereas the design of tools is typically framed as a *user-centered* design problem, the design of human-object collectives can be defined as a *practice-centered* design

problem. We envision object-centered sociality as a theoretical position with strong potentiality to extend the user-centered approach, especially in the design of interactive systems. We argue that *repositioning users with smart artifacts*, regarding both as participants in collective activity in interactive systems, will enhance the domain of interaction design beyond instrumental goals, the design of distributed ubiquitous computing systems, and the elicitation of social interaction by smart tangible means.

By proposing object-centered sociality as a basis for design, we argue that objects play a significant role in constituting the social context in which the modern individual interacts. As for researchers in a lab, people's everyday activities gravitate around objects that help them to represent themselves as members of multiple communities. The commuting mode I use daily, the sports I follow, and the market shares I own are instances of what Knorr-Cetina calls *knowledge objects* (Knorr-Cetina, 1997). She contends that such objects are increasingly mediating human relationships and adopting social roles, thereby constituting society's cohesive glue in the contemporary era of 'objectualized' social individualization.

The very notion of *object* is discussed here. If we are to think seriously about understanding how sociality is shared with objects, alternative understandings of what objects and artifacts are and what they do in society needs to be considered. Commodities and instruments are two traditional concepts that define an object in terms of an element of the marketplace or a component of our equipment toolbox. Any forms of sociality emerging from those concepts will evolve pointing

towards the notions of economic value and pragmatic utility. Design practitioners understand this well, and designers have successfully implemented this understanding in products and services available at the market place. Our research is structured along a different conceptual perspective. It does not intend to contradict nor controvert a designerly understanding of artifacts but rather features ideas that invite us to regard the artificial world that surrounds us from the perspective of a designer interested in using artifacts as means for social exchange, adaptive signs for solidarity, or equipment for cooperation.

We discuss two logics that shape the role of artifacts in the human-technology relationship. On the one hand, we have the user-centered approach which regards humans as users positioned at the center of a technological system. On the other hand, we propose a post-humanist approach that de-centers humans as the sole *participants* in the social group of human and nonhuman actors in which such system's acts and practices are collectively enacted. For this analysis we begin by considering in parallel two paradigmatic analyses of a door: Norman's door analysis in *The Design of Everyday Things* (Norman, 2002) which represents the user-centered approach, and Latour's door analysis in *Mixing Humans and Nonhumans Together: The Sociology of a Door-Closer* (Latour (Jim Johnson), 1988) which represents the post-humanist approach.

We discuss how post-human repositioning of *users* opens up how action can be constituted in a network of human and nonhuman actors. Finally we offer a conceptual framework for the design of smart artifacts based on the proposed *object-centered sociality approach*.

HUMAN ASPECTS OF DOORKNOBS

The term *user-centered design* was first introduced by Norman and Draper (Norman & Draper, 1986), and subsequently elaborated by Norman (Norman, 2002). The central question around which Norman's idea gravitates is: How do people cope effectively with everyday things?

(Norman, 2002, p.12) In his analysis, Norman refers to several artifacts of which the door persists as a distinctive example. He suggests that we should be able to open and close the majority of instances of interactions with a door and not be deceived in the attempt. His claim is valid since a door is a mundane object that does not require a trained user to operate it. This claim implies that any door, particularly its knobs or handles, should convey the same interpretation in its users' minds. Moreover, it also implies a sort of cognitive homogeneity in the population of door users - a desirable condition for those who define standards and norms.

Norman argues that there are three sources of knowledge for answering his question. First, the psychology of human thought and cognition, which argues that humans elaborate conceptual models that allow us to predict the effects of our actions. Second, the psychology of everyday things, which claims that humans can map the relationship between their actions and their effects in the world. And third, the design of the artifact, which should provide us with feedback about what action we have actually performed upon it.

Based on the analysis of these sources of knowledge, Norman offers an approximated model of human action from which he introduces some design strategies to support action planning for human-artifact interaction. Such design strategies argue for the explicit representation of the artifact's current state and operational model, the correct mapping of a user's mental model with the artifact's operational model, and prompt feedback from the artifact. For Abras, Maloney-Krichmar and Preece (Abras *et al*, 2004), such strategies place the user at the center of the design process, suggesting that the designer's goal is to facilitate the task for the user, reducing his or her cognitive and physical efforts in using the artifact.

The fundamental concept underlying Norman's user-centered design is that the knowledge necessary to execute our actions and achieve our goals is distributed partially in our brain, partially in the world as reified affordances and partially in

the constraints we encounter in the world. By that line of thought, the design of a door should be framed by the mental model that potential users have about how a door should work, the user's plan of action in which the door is involved, the interface of the artifact represented by all of the touch points between the user and the door, and finally the potential constraints that the door might offer to restrict the user's action.

That is perfectly reasonable, but where in that picture of cognitive capacities, mental models, plans, actions, affordances and constraints do fit the social aspects of the door such as privacy, security, restriction, isolation and invitation? The main argument of user-centered design is to make the system more usable, make the user's action more efficient, and minimize the chances of operational deception. But it appears that other aspects of social action, that are less related to an actor's psychology and bodily capacities, and more

related to his or her necessity of belonging, contributing, cooperating or even conflicting, are not apprehended by the paradigm of the user-centered design.

More recently, Norman reviewed his concept of affordance and reformulated his original question arguing that affordances do not respond to the question: how do people cope effectively with everyday situations? (Norman, 2008, 2011). His answer is that affordances are fine for artifacts but in social or cultural situations it is necessary to look for *social signifiers*. The discussion in the design community around the concept of affordance, originally introduced in psychology by Gibson (Gibson, 1979/1986), has been extensive and vivid (Hartson, 2003). Norman is now taking some reflective distance from the concept of affordance and adopting the concept of *signifier* instead. A signifier is "some sort of indicator, some signal in the physical or social world that can be

Figures 1a and 1b. Distribution of action among participants. Towards Smart Artifact - Human - Nonhuman collectives.

interpreted meaningfully" (Norman, 2011, p. 89). Moreover, a signifier is social when it "is either created or interpreted by people or society, signifying social activity or appropriate social behavior" (Norman, 2008, p. 18).

As an example, in Figure 1a, User 1 has the intention of getting inside the room and his plan is to walk in. But he encounters the door, in one of its possible states: closed, partially-open, or open. Up until that point, the door's state is a social signifier to be interpreted by the User 1. Any of those states can be the intended result of User 2's action, who wants to convey his intention of either allowing to be disturbed or not.

Norman's new question opens onto inquiry on actors' capacity to deal successfully with a social situation, a clear reorientation of his initial functionalistic inquiry towards the semiotic aspect of others' actions. The analysis of the usability of the doorknob is now shifted to the interpretation of encountering a door closed or open. This is exactly the point we want to extend further: we are not only suggesting analysis of the meaning of the door situation - open or closed - in relation to one's action but further proposing to analyze the mediational role of the door in relation to the one who closed the door and its effect upon the action of someone who encounters the closed door.

SOCIAL ASPECTS OF DOOR HINGES

To continue with the same object of Norman's case study, we now turn our attention to the analysis by Latour about the sociology of a door-closer (Latour (Jim Johnson), 1988). The argumentative strategy used by Latour is to make a parallel between the function performed by a mechanical door-closer, and the number of people and work necessary to perform the same function if only human actors are employed. In order to simplify his description, he makes reference only to fundamental components such as springs and hinges, yet disregarding some others like the lock and other structural parts.

We focus our attention on the social dynamics articulated and co-shaped by artifacts - in this

case a door that divides and connects two architectural spaces. We are not interested in the networks of actors involved in engineering and manufacturing the parts of an artifact, nor in the orchestration of the bureaucracy necessary to put them together. Our attempt here is to intersect the user-centered design inquiry about how humans cope with unfamiliar social situations with the concept of distributed action in networks of human and nonhuman actors from Actor-Network Theory.

Actor-Network Theory (ANT) is a sociological theory developed by Bruno Latour, Michel Callon and John Law, among others, since the 1980s and known by its current name in the late 1990s. ANT contends that society is constituted by networked humans and nonhumans actors regarded symmetrically. Such symmetry entails that the capacity of action in society is endowed to both human and nonhumans. Anything that modifies the current state of affairs by effecting others' action is an actor. The way nonhumans act is not to be intended as causal action. ANT does not claim that artifacts plan actions. The meaning of nonhuman action is revealed as artifacts "allow, afford, encourage, permit, suggest, influence, block, render possible, forbid [...]" states of affairs (Latour, 2005, p. 72). Albeit nonhuman agency seems contradictory, it is brought forth in the analysis of the *programs-of-action* that are effected by the participation of artifacts (Callon & Law, 1995). From this perspective, *the social* occurs in the interaction between actants - both humans and nonhumans - characterized as intermediaries or mediators (Latour, 1999).

A *program-of-action* is a script of what an actant can do. In the case of a human, a program-of-action is associated with his or her intention. This idea intersects Norman's definition of *plan*. In Figure 1b, Participant 1 has the intention of getting inside the room and his program-of-action is influenced by Participant 2 - the door, that mediates between the intentions of both Participants 1 and 3.

The program-of-action of the door, as a nonhuman artifact, obstructs Participant 1's execution of his program-of-action and represents the intention of the Participant 3. The door's program-of-action is the result of its association with other actants. In the example depicted in Figure 1b, Participant 3 delegates his or her program of action into the door constituting a collective.

Figure 2. Four possible collectives of humans and nonhumans

When two or more actants interact and their programs-of-action are associated, a *collective* is constituted. The new collective's program-of-action is the *translation* of the parent actors' programs-of-action. In Figure 2 we show four possibilities: a) a single doorman who opens the door when required, b) well mannered door users who knock on the door before entering the room, c) a door tag added to the door, and finally d) a door with a mechanical door-closer.

In the above scenario, the role of a designer is to define the attributes of the door and other nonhuman actors that can potentially enact a desired state of affairs when the door interacts with a human. The result of the design process contends the *inscription* of a program-of-action in the nonhuman's design and the *prescription* of the suitable forms of user action. As an example, the mechanical door-closer is inscribed to constantly push the door to the closed position. Such inscription prescribes that the door can be open only if the user exerts a stronger opposite force.

When human and nonhuman actors interact, there is a direct correlation between the quality of the program-of-action inscribed in the nonhuman actor and the human skills needed to achieve a

goal. The poorer design the artifact has, the more a highly skilled human user is necessary to successfully operate it. In the door example, a child or a parent with a stroller can have serious problems trying to open the door or pass through the threshold if the strength of the door-closer's spring is not damped to prevent the door of swinging back too fast. This exemplifies the

distribution of skills among the members of a human-nonhuman collective.

TRACING BACK THE ACTOR'S ACTION

Now it is possible to picture the deployment of actants and their chains of action. It is in the metaphor of a network where it is possible to represent the interconnected nature of all of the participants of not only a single action but several actions running in parallel. Albeit all those actors are enacting their programs-of-action, they are not necessarily aligned to cooperate, or synchronized to collaborate. The outcome of this network is a social situation imprinted in the artifacts - as signifiers, but at the same time co-shaped by them - as mediators, together with the human participants in the actor-network.

To answer the question formulated by Norman about how do we cope effectively with everyday situations, it is necessary to understand what the world affords to us, the users. But, moreover, it is fundamental to understand the meaning of one's action in the ecology of its human and nonhuman participants. By dislocating the user's central position and distributing his or her hegemony in a network of participants, designers will get a better understanding of what people need in order

to cope with social situations, and inscribe in artifacts better socially suited programs-of-action.

THE STRUCTURE OF COLLECTIVES

We offer a triadic structure of social relationships of human-artifact collectives (see Figure 3) in which two of the three participants in the social interaction are instances of a human agent who are interacting with an artifact. One of the human participants sets a technological relationship with the artifact constituting a collective. As a result, the triadic structure is always composed by a bracketed human-artifact(s) collective acting upon other participants.

Figure 3 Structure of a human-smart artifact collective triad

Figure 3 represents the foundational structure in which *H* stands for a human agent and *other(s)* stands for the other individual or collective party (human or nonhuman). In this structure we are introducing a smart artifact as a nonhuman participant, instead of a simple artifact, because our research interest is in the design of smart devices that enable social interaction. In the door example, the smart artifact would be a smart door that reads the social setting and adapts itself to facilitate social interaction. A more comprehensive definition of smart artifact will be introduced later.

Connecting this triadic structure with the example discussed above, Participant 3 and the door get involved in a *technological relationship*. Their interaction is described as a *meaningful form of mediation* with Participant 1. Because Participant

3 wants to be alone, he closes the door and hangs the 'Do not disturb' tag on the doorknob. In that operation he delegates to the door-door tag assemblage the control of his privacy. When Participant 1 on his way to the room encounters the door closed with the tag of 'No Disturbance' displayed, his action is blocked requiring a *type of social action* such as 'knocking the door and asking for permission to enter'.

The technological relation between the human and the smart artifact is represented by a hyphen (-) in Figure 3. Following Ihde (Ihde, 1990), embodiment, hermeneutic, and alterity relations are technological relations of the same continuum in which they represent different levels of human-artifact relations. We contend that such a continuum depicts different levels of an artifact's *presence* (see Figure 4). At one end of the continuum the artifact is almost non-present (ready-to hand) and the human party might be unaware of it. On the opposite end of the continuum the smart artifact is present (present-at-hand) and the human party's intentionality is addressed towards it. Between these two extremes are hermeneutic relations, in which the smart artifact is present to be read.

The relation *H-smart artifact*, can be mapped into the continuum and interpreted in three archetypical ways:

- **Embodiment relations** in which *the artifact and H constitute an embodied unit*. For example, cybernetic individuals who make explicit their internal condition by using wearable technologies (Schiphorst, 2006).
- **Hermeneutic relations** in which *H reads what the smart artifact interprets*. As an example, a recommendation website such as yelp.com aggregates opinions and

Figure 4 Continuum of human-artifact technological relation

evaluations of multiple users of several services available in a particular city. This website offers synthesized rankings that may help any citizen or visitor to make decisions about the services available at that city based on the consolidated results (Shirky, 2008).

- **Alterity relations** in which *H* acts regarding the smart artifact as a quasi-other. For example, robots that engage in social exchanges with humans (Breazeal, 2002).

The meaning of mediation of the human-nonhuman collectives described by ANT can be of four types: translation, composition, black-boxing and delegation. In Figure 3, the collective bracketed within curly braces, enacts one of these types of mediation whenever it executes a type of social action. These aspects of mediation are clearly defined by Latour (see Latour, 2005).

The forms of social action of interest in this research are coordination, cooperation, adhesion and conflict resolution. They are represented in Figure 3 by a bi-directional arrow. Although other forms of social action are possible, these four are representative of the main interest of this project. *Coordination* is a form of social action in which two or more actors synchronize their actions even though they may have different goals. *Cooperation* is observed when two or more actors act collectively in order to achieve a common goal. *Adhesion* is the inclusion of a new actor in a group of actors that pursue a common goal. Finally, *conflict resolution* is observed when two or more actors need the same resource but it is only available for some of them.

A DEFINITION OF SMART ARTIFACTS

A smart artifact is a structurally determined agent that autonomously acts in the world by adapting its programs-of-action. Every smart artifact is designed by someone or a team that assigns to it one or many programs-of-action. In doing so, the designer or design team defines the artifact's organization and structure (following Maturana &

Varela, 1992). The structure of a smart artifact is characterized as a set of sensors and affordances. Its sensors perceive the state of the artifact and other actors in their context. Its affordances afford or constraint its interaction with social actors.

A smart artifact gets involved in human social activity by taking part in the social actions performed by people. When the smart artifact's program-of-action is articulated with those of other agents, a collective is constituted. As a social actor, the role of a smart-artifact is twofold. On the one hand, it is regarded as an apparatus that can get involved in social interactions. As such, its relation with humans can be explained by the forms of human relationship with technology put forward by Ihde (Ihde, 1990) and extended further by Verbeek (Verbeek, 2005). On the other hand, the smart artifact is regarded as a member of a collective. As such, its form of social mediation can be explained by ANT meanings of technical mediation.

SMART ARTIFACTS INVOLVED IN SOCIAL ACTION

The methodological advantage of using programs-of-action as descriptive scripts of what an actor can do is that they are designed to have predictable outcomes. As Latour argues, nonhuman actors have their programs-of-action inscribed. At the same time they prescribe how human actors can interact with them. At the moment a human actor adopts the prescribed role, he or she gets subscribed to that prescription. As an example, while writing a book the author prescribes the future existence of a reader. When a person adopts the position of the reader he or she is subscribed to that prescription.

The mechanism used by the smart artifact to yield the meaning of other actors is based on Schutz' analysis of action and meaning (Schutz, 1972). Schutz contends that an action is composed of discrete acts. Hence, if a series of acts have relational attributes that link them to each other act, then all of those acts belong to the same *meaning-context*. The basic relational attributes for an act to be considered part of the same

action are its indexicality (space), contemporaneity (time), and course of action. The course of an action is the set of actions and interactions that have contributed to the evolution of a phenomena.

As an example, the action *smoking a cigarette* is constituted by discrete acts such as putting the cigarette in the mouth, lighting a lighter, lighting the cigarette, extinguishing the lighter, smoking the cigarette and extinguishing the cigarette. Any act of one's own experience of smoking that share the characteristics of smoking-a-cigarette-arc-of-action belongs to the same *meaning-context*. If a group of people are found recursively at an outdoors spot with a box of cigarettes at hand lighting up cigarettes with a smart lighter, an action pattern is constituted. Then, it is possible for the smart lighter to predict that someone will need to enact its program-of-action every time someone finds himself or herself in the same circumstances. Based in that prediction the smart lighter can activate its mechanisms to render itself affordable.

SOCIALITY WITH OBJECTS AND ARTIFACTS

Finally, we want to introduce an alternative notion of *object* that better defines the kind of artifact that signifies and mediates social interaction. Two notions of object that are traditionally used in the social sciences are commodities and instruments. On the one hand, commodities tend to be defined in a logic of value and exchange. On the other hand, instruments are defined as tools or equipment serving to accomplish a practical purpose. They are the necessary means to cope with the world; hence, their logic is fundamentally instrumental. Knorr-Cetina offers *knowledge objects* as an alternative notion of object based on Rheinberger's study of expert communities. As researchers in the lab, people socialize around things they want to understand and explain. Those things are defined as incomplete and continuously unfolding units positioned at the center of the society's structure. In Knorr-Cetina's words, objects of knowledge are "characteristically open, question-generating and complex. [...] [They] seem to have the capacity to

unfold indefinitely. [...] [T]hey continually acquire new properties and change the ones they have" (Knorr-Cetina, 1997, p. 12).

Knorr-Cetina theorizes knowledge objects as a dynamic structure that can never be attained. Therefore, on the subject side, "this lack corresponds to a structure of wanting, a continually renewed interest in knowing that appears to be never fulfilled by final knowledge" (Knorr-Cetina, 1997, p. 13). In other words, the subject is constantly trying to satisfy his or her desire of knowing more about such an object.

We envision material instantiations of knowledge objects as smart artifacts that continually unfold while preserving their organization. In that sense, they can be instantiated as signifying artifacts, material things that evolve, mutate, and transform preserving their condition as objects of inquiry. The door, for instance, is constantly constituting and dissolving collectives and conveying different meanings.

CONCLUSION

Whereas user-centered design denies the ascription of control to artifacts assuming humans as the acting party, object-centered sociality is open to distributing the system's actions in a network of actors that includes artifacts. This can certainly contribute to design and research in ubiquitous computing and smart artifacts because humans are dislocated from being the *users of* to being among the *participants in* a distributed system.

Latour's domain of action embraces Norman's and extends it. Whereas for the user-centered approach the domain of action is constrained to the user's plan of action, Latour broadens the domain of action to multiple forms of participant intervention in a network of actors.

The notion of a program-of-action, although initially formulated in Actor-Network Theory, is applicable to design of affordances and constraints. To Latour, the program-of-action is delegated to nonhuman actors and enacted by

humans, whereas to Norman, the program-of-action is inscribed in the artifact's affordances and constraints with which the user interacts. We suggest that the design of smart artifacts can be enriched by rethinking affordances and constraints as mechanisms for distributed human-nonhuman collective action.

The social interaction design framework that we offer implements an object-centered sociality approach which extrapolates Norman's model of action to a network of human and nonhuman actors while building upon formal models of social action.

Finally, the articulation of an object-centered sociality approach with interaction design methods opens up the user-artifact dyad by embracing diverse kinds of participants and practices, thus facilitating the design of mediated social interaction.

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